

INFLUENCE LOCAL TAXES AND LEVIES ON LOCAL REVENUE THROUGH ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NORTH SUMATRA PROVINCE

VEBRY M LUMBAN GAOL^{1*}, AUDREY M. SIAHAAN²,
HAMONANGAN SIALLAGAN³, HALOMOAN SIHOMBING⁴ and
CRISTIAN GOKLAS NABABAN⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Universitas HKBP Nommensen.

*Corresponding Author Email: vebry.lumbangaol@uhn.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to influence local taxes and levies on local revenue through economic growth in North Sumatra Province in 2019-2023. This type of research is quantitative. The data used is secondary data with data collection techniques using documentation techniques. The sample selection method in this study uses saturated sampling method. The data analysis technique used in this research is to use SmartPLS 4.0. The results of this study indicate that local taxes and local levies both have a positive and significant effect on local revenue while economic growth has no effect on local revenue. However, local retribution has no positive and significant effect on regional economic growth. Then regional economic growth cannot mediate local taxes and local retribution with local revenue.

Keywords: Local Taxes, Levies Taxes, Local Revenue, Economic Growth.

INTRODUCTION

In the implementation of regional autonomy, provincial governments and including district and city governments have great authority to develop and manage their own territories, with the main focus on increasing local revenue (PAD) and emphasizing their independence. State and local taxes consist of taxes levied at the subfederal government level to finance state and local public services, which gives discretion in the determination of tax rates and bases to subfederal governments. (Feld & Schneider, 2001a). Since the implementation of the autonomous government system in Indonesia for regions that are considered to have the capacity to be independent, the government will give permission for the formation of new autonomous regions in accordance with the regulations stipulated in the law, specifically related to the formation of autonomous regions. (Mendy, 2024) Regional Original Revenue (PAD) is a source of income for local governments that is used to finance regional expenditures and development in their respective regions.

Regional autonomy allows local governments to organize government and serve the community according to their goals, so as to improve services and benefits. (Ardianto et al., n.d.) Local taxes as part of regional autonomy cannot be separated from the concept of decentralization, because autonomy is a manifestation of decentralization. Autonomy comes from the Greek “auto” which means own, and “nomos” which means law or power. Sumaryadi defines regional autonomy as “legal self-sufficiency and true independence” in the Encyclopedia of Social Sciences (Sumaryadi, 2005).

The primary function of local governments is to provide public goods and services, including education, hospitals and health services, transportation (roads, public transport), public safety (police, fire), parks, community development and planning, waste management, and other infrastructure (McDonald, 2012).

Local taxes and levies play a crucial role in driving the local economy and supporting local government budgets. Local revenue (PAD) derived from these two sources forms the backbone of development programs at the local level. North Sumatra Province, as part of Indonesia, faces significant challenges in managing and optimizing revenues from local taxes and levies to achieve sustainable economic growth. In terms of revenue, successful local finance is when local finance is able to increase local revenue sustainably in line with economic development in the area without worsening the allocation of factors of production and a sense of justice in society and at the cost of obtaining local revenue effectively and efficiently (Joni Fernandes, n.d.). Tax systems are not just the result of historical events, political and institutional factors add to a positive understanding of the types of taxes used by subfederal jurisdictions (Feld & Schneider, 2001b).

An important factor to consider in achieving regional self-sufficiency is the allocation of capital expenditure. Increasing the portion of capital expenditure in the form of fixed assets, including infrastructure, equipment, facilities, and infrastructure, is very important to increase economic productivity because the higher the capital expenditure, the higher the economic productivity. (Sriwijayanti & Apriyanti, n.d.)

The policy basically expands the regions to explore their own sources of local revenue from the components of local taxes and levies. In principle, the fiscal decentralization policy expects the dependence of local governments on the central government to be reduced, so as to achieve regional independence as the achievement of the autonomy goal itself (Hartono et al., n.d.)

**Ratio of Regional Original Revenue (PAD) to Regional Revenue in North Sumatram
2019-2023**

Year	Regional Original Revenue (In thousands)	Regional Revenue (in thousands)	Ratio of PAD to Regional Revenue
2019	5.763.154.073.091	13.081.482.296.509	44,06%
2020	5.531.237.378.775	12.916.359.750.491	42,82%
2021	6.402.714.086.507	14.034.036.628.477	45,62%
2022	7.258.018.251.933	12.594.412.688.862	57,63%
2023	9.570.226.151.361	12.798.607.945.004	74,78%

Based on the table above, in 2019, the ratio of Regional Original Revenue (PAD) to regional income reached 44.06%, then in 2020 it fell to 42.82%. The ratio rose again in 2021 to 45.62%. And the increase in the ratio can also be seen in 2023 to 74.78%, the ratio between PAD to total regional income shows the dependency ratio of a region. Meanwhile, in the 2020 fiscal year it decreased when compared to the previous year. From the data obtained, the revenue of local taxes and levies of North Sumatra Province as part of the source of revenue for Regional Original Revenue has decreased, this is due to the non-achievement of the 2020 local tax and levy budget target, which is strongly influenced by the extraordinary conditions of the COVID-

19 Pandemic which caused the national economic growth rate to contract to minus 5% in the second quarter of 2020. The higher the ratio of PAD to total revenue, the smaller the dependence of a region on the transfer of funds from external parties, both the central government and other local governments. So it can be concluded that from 2019 to 2022 the dependence of the region on the center is increasing or it can be said that the independence of the North Sumatra region is of high value.

Traditional fiscal decentralization theory suggests that, compared to the central government, local governments are closer to the electorate and have information advantages such as easy identification of the needs and preferences of the population and an understanding of the costs of providing public services in their jurisdictions (Faguet, 2014).

Other scholars prove that only by reasonably matching tax and expenditure responsibilities and establishing sound accountability mechanisms, fiscal decentralization is conducive to efficiently allocating public resources and improving public welfare (Oates, 1973). However, other case-based studies have found that local governments under fiscal decentralization engage in fierce tax competition, which will increase infrastructure investment and reduce the proportion of livelihood-based public service expenditure (Sanogo, 2019).

The negative impact of fiscal decentralization is that local governments under fiscal decentralization engage in fierce tax competition, which will increase infrastructure investment and reduce the proportion of livelihood-based public service expenditures, resulting in systematic distortions in the fiscal expenditure structure. Therefore, the negative impact of government on public service provision cannot be ignored, especially in developing countries (Skidmore & Toya, 2013).

(Al Hafiz et al., n.d.) Synergies between local government and BUMDs need to be strengthened through better planning and coordination in order to optimally achieve development goals and public welfare. These findings underscore the important role of BUMDs in supporting the success of regional economic development and the need for strategic actions to improve their performance and contribution in supporting regional financial independence.

Realization of Regional Original Revenue of North Sumatra Province in 2019-2023

Year	Budget	Realization	Persentase (%)
2019	14.034.339.344.970	13.081.482.296.509	93,21%
2020	13.077.362.353.824	12.916.359.750.491	98,77%
2021	13.687.123.662.525	14.034.036.628.477	102,53%
2022	12.459.352.172.672	12.594.412.688.862	101,08%
2023	13.458.522.513.391	12.798.607.945.004	95,10%

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the realization of PAD in 2019 was only IDR 13.081 Trillion or 93.21%, so it can be said that PAD 2019 was unable to meet the targeted amount of PAD of IDR 14.034 Trillion. In 2022 the North Sumatra Provincial Government lowered the PAD target from Rp 13.077 Trillion to 12.459 Trillion, but from the table it can be seen that the realization of PAD finally met the lowered target. The PAD target for 2023 increased the PAD target but the realization was 95.10%. This target mismatch is due to the

fact that there are still sources of PAD that have not been maximally utilized. This shows various indications of weaknesses in various aspects of management. The results of previous research obtained state that indications of these weaknesses include: 1) Weak revenue planning and target setting due to inaccurate data and information; 2) Uncertainty in the realization of levies on the object of tax and levy collection 3) Factors of less than optimal supervision and control (Ekarin & Soetrisno, 2024).

LITERATURE

Local taxes, local levies and local revenue

Based on Law Number 28 of 2009, local taxes (PD) are taxpayer contributions to the regions owed by individuals or entities that are compelling based on law by not getting direct rewards and are used for regional purposes for the greatest prosperity of the people.

According to (Mardiasmo, 2021) the definition of local tax is a mandatory contribution to the region owed by persons or entities that are compelling based on the law by not getting a direct reward and used for regional purposes for the greatest prosperity of the people. (Rendhika Adhiyatama, n.d.) reveals that local taxes are mandatory contributions made by individuals or entities to the region without direct balanced rewards that can be implemented based on applicable laws and regulations, which are used to finance the implementation of local government and regional development.

The legal basis that regulates local levies (RD) is the same as local taxes, namely Law Number 28 of 2009 concerning Local Taxes (PD) and Local Levies (RD). Like local taxes, local user charges are also one of the important sources of local revenue to finance the implementation of local government. Retribution can be defined as a levy made by the government as a result of the contra achievement provided by the local government or the payment is based on the achievement or service provided by the local government which is directly enjoyed individually by citizens and its implementation is based on applicable regulations (Rifai & Priono, 2022a). Based on Law Number 33 of 2004 concerning Financial Balance between Central and Regional Governments, Article 1 number 18, Regional Original Revenue is revenue obtained by the region and collected based on local regulations in accordance with statutory regulations. Local own-source revenues are revenues obtained by regions that are levied based on local regulations in accordance with statutory regulations to raise funds for the needs of the regions concerned in financing their activities.

Regional Original Revenue (PAD) is all regional revenue sourced from the region's own original economy. (Asyah Harisandi et al., 2024)

Meanwhile, according to (Mardiasmo, 2021) is revenue sourced from the regional tax sector, regional levies, the results of regionally owned companies, the results of the management of separated regional assets, and other legitimate local revenue. Regional Original Revenue (PAD) is revenue obtained from regional potential both from the tax sector, levies or legitimate regional results that are used for regional funding and development.

Regional Economic Growth (PED)

According to (Sadono Sukirno, 2016) Economic Growth is a quantitative measure that describes the development of the economy in a given year when compared to the previous year. Theoretical and empirical literature has shown that good and efficient governments contribute to economic development at the national level (Shen et al., 2021) or at the regional level (Chen & Li, 2018). Indeed, good and efficient government spending and transfers, as well as non-distorting taxes can fulfill consumer preferences more accurately, but this also means that more or better public goods and services are allocated with the same level of spending (Wang et al., 2024). Based on the understanding put forward by several experts above, it can be concluded that regional economic growth is the growth rate of production of goods and services indicated by the growth rate of gross regional domestic product in a region calculated at constant prices where the rate of economic growth itself is compared with the previous economic growth rate.

Figure 1: conceptual framework

METHODS

This type of research uses quantitative methods. The type of data used is secondary data, which is quantitative data which includes data on local taxes, local levies, economic growth, and local revenue obtained from the official website of the North Sumatra Central Statistics Agency (BPS) with data collection techniques using documentation techniques. The population used in this study were all regencies / cities in North Sumatra Province, totaling 33 regions. The data used is the Realization of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) and Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) data during 2019-2023.

The number of analysis units in this study were 165 units. The data analysis method used in this research is Partial Least Square (PLS) - SEM using SmartPLS software version 4.0.

SmartPLS software was used as a data analysis tool in this study. This analysis uses Structural Equation Modeling techniques.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a statistical technique that is able to analyze the pattern of relationships between latent constructs and their indicators, latent constructs with each other, and direct measurement errors. (Hair et al., 2018)

SEM allows analysis between several dependent variables and independent variables directly. It is important to evaluate the measurement model and structural model before testing. Measurement model or measurement model is part of the SEM model that describes the relationship between latent variables and their indicators.

Straight arrows show the relationship from latent variables towards each indicator. In addition, there are also straight arrows from error and disturbance terms towards their respective variables, as well as no direct influence or straight arrows connecting latent variables.

Research Variables

1. The dependent variable in this study is local own-source revenue (PAD). Every Any income or revenue received by the regional treasury originating from sources within the region itself, levied in accordance with existing laws and regulations, and used for regional purposes is referred to as Regional Original Revenue Regional Original Revenue stems from (Nilam Kencana Ningrat & Supadmi, 2019). Meanwhile, according to (Mardiasmo, 2021) is revenue sourced from the regional tax sector, regional levies, the results of regionally owned companies, the results of the management of separated regional assets, and other legitimate regional original income.
2. The independent variables in this study are local taxes (PD) and Levies Tax (RD). Local tax is a mandatory contribution to the region owed by individuals or entities that are compelling based on the law by not getting a direct reward and used for regional purposes for the greatest prosperity of the people. This definition is contained in the Regional Tax and Regional Retribution Law Number 28 of 2009.

According to (Windhu Putra, 2018) regional contributions are contributions paid by the people to the regions that can be imposed which get a direct return achievement. According to (Hantono et al., 2021) Regional contributions are local levies as payment for services or granting certain permits specifically provided and / or granted by the local government for the benefit of individuals or entities. Local levies, in particular, embody a transactional relationship between the government and its citizens, where payments made by citizens for government services realize real direct benefits - an aspect that needs to be underlined (Nisa et al., 2020). The Intervening Variable is Economic Growth (PED). The definition of economic growth says that economic growth can be seen as an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one period of time to another. (Raisová & Ďurčová, 2014)

Increasing production is essential for economic growth, but this production responds to, not leads, demand growth. The authors' view of growth differs from conventional theory-we seek to understand the causes and processes of economic growth. (Hudson, 2020)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model and Hypothesis Testing

Model and hypothesis testing was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS (PLS) software version 4.0. The following are the stages of data processing in this study:

Assessing the Outer Model Figure 2 Structural Model

Source: SmartPLS version 4.0 data processing results

Based on the presentation of the picture above, the indicators with latent constructs show that the study uses reflective indicators, because all indicators move the same, which means that changes in one indicator cause changes to other indicators. Between constructs shows the relationship to be studied (hypothesis).

Validity Test

The validity test through convergent validity with the SmartPLS 4.0 program can be seen from the outerloading and loading factor values. The loading factor value that reaches > 0.7 means that the indicator is valid in measuring its construct, so it can be said to be ideal. However, in the early stages of research from the development of the measurement scale stage, the loading factor value of 0.5 to 0.6 can be considered sufficient. (Ghozali, 2018) The following is a diagram of the loading factor value of each indicator in the research model.

Table 1: Outer Loading Results

	PAD (Y)	PD (X1)	PED (Z)	RD (X2)
LN PAD	1.000			
LN PD		1.000		
LN PED			1.000	
LN RD				1.000

Based on the presentation of the table above, it shows that all construct indicators have an outer value above 0.5. Indicators of all constructs have an outer loading value of 1,000, this indicates that all indicators are valid and meet convergent validity. (Ghozali, 2018)

Based on the image presentation, it depicts the relationship between indicators and latent variables. Discriminant validity of the measurement model with reflexive indicators is assessed based on crossloading measurements with constructs.

Table 2: Loading Factor Value

	PAD (Y)	PD (X1)	PED (Z)	RD (X2)
PAD (Y)	1.000			
PD (X1)	0.895	1.000		
PED (Z)	0.827	0.910	1.000	
RD (X2)	0.638	0.610	0.581	1.000

Another method for assessing *discriminant validity* is to compare the *square root* value of the *average variance extracted* (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. The *average variance extracted* (AVE) value must be above 0.50.

Apart from observing the *cross loading* value, *discriminant validity* can also be determined through another method, namely by looking at the *average variant extracted* (AVE) value for each indicator, it is required that the value must be > 0.5 for a good model.

Hypothesis Test

Table Path Coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Value)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
PD (X1) -> PAD (Y)	0,760	0,748	0,096	7,912	0,000
PD (X1) -> PED (Z)	0,884	0,879	0,032	27,287	0,000
PED (Z) -> PAD (Y)	0,052	0,060	0,087	0,594	0,553
RD (X2) -> PAD (Y)	0,144	0,145	0,034	4,183	0,000
RD (X2) -> PED (Z)	0,042	0,047	0,040	1,065	0,287

The table above shows that the effect of PD (Regional Tax) on PAD (Regional Original Revenue) is 0.760 and significant at 0.05 ($7.912 > 1.974$). The effect of PD (Regional Revenue) on PED (Regional Economic Growth) is 0.884 and significant at 0.05 ($27.287 > 1.974$).

The effect of PED (Regional Economic Growth) on PAD (Regional Original Revenue) is 0.052 and not significant at 0.05 ($0.594 < 1.974$). The effect of RD (Regional Retribution) on PAD (Regional Original Revenue) is 0.114 and significant at 0.05 ($4.183 > 1.974$). The effect of RD (Local Retribution) on PED (Regional Economic Growth) is 0.042 and not significant at 0.05 ($1.065 < 1.974$).

DISCUSSION

1. Local tax and local retribution have a positive and significant influence simultaneously on local revenue. This means that the more the amount of local taxes increases, the more local revenue will increase. Conversely, if local taxes decrease, then local revenue is also low. The results of this research are in line with research conducted previously by and show that local taxes have a significant positive effect on local revenue.
2. Local taxes have a partial effect on regional economic growth. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by. Meanwhile, local levies have no effect on regional economic growth. In line with research conducted by
3. The results of the *bootstrapping* test show that the regional economic growth variable cannot mediate the effect of local taxes and local retributions on local revenue.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that local taxes and local levies both have a positive and significant effect on local revenue while economic growth has no effect on local revenue.

However, local retribution has no positive and significant effect on regional economic growth. Then regional economic growth cannot mediate local taxes and local retribution with local revenue.

Suggestion

1. For the community, it is expected to increase compliance in paying local tax obligations and local levies. It is hoped that the results of the local revenue component will also be used for the benefit of the state and society in infrastructure development efforts. So that with the higher compliance of the community in paying taxes and levies, it means that the community has contributed to developing their region and contributing to efforts to improve the welfare of the region where the community lives.
2. For the North Sumatra provincial government, it is hoped that it can become input material in the implementation of regional financial management in order to further increase the collection and acceptance of each component of local revenue

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